

EFFECT OF WATER ABSORPTION ON TIME-TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT STRENGTH OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP

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Keywords: CFRP, Static strength, Water absorption, Time-temperature dependence

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) are now being used for the primary structures of airplanes, ships and others, in which the high reliability should be kept during the long-term operation. Therefore, it would be expected that the accelerated testing methodology for the long-term life prediction of CFRP structures exposed under the actual environments of temperature, water, and others must be established.

We have proposed a general and rigorous advanced accelerated testing methodology (ATM-2) which can be applied to the life prediction of CFRP exposed to an actual load and environment history based on the three conditions. One of these conditions is the fact that the time and temperature dependence on the strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin [1]. The formulations of creep compliance and time-temperature shift factors of matrix resin are carried out based on the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP). The formulations of long-term life of CFRP under an actual loading are carried out based on the three conditions.

In this paper, the tensile and compressive static strengths in the longitudinal and transverse directions of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP under wet condition are evaluated using ATM-2. The applicability of ATM-2 and the effect of water absorption on time and temperature dependence of these static strengths are discussed.

2 Advanced Accelerated Testing Methodology (ATM-2)

ATM-2 is established with following three conditions: (A) the failure probability is independent of time, temperature and load history [2]; (B) the time and temperature dependence of strength of CFRP is controlled by the viscoelasticity of matrix resin. Therefore, the TTSP for the viscoelasticity of matrix resin holds for the strength of CFRP; (C) the strength degradation of CFRP holds the linear cumulative damage law as the cumulative damage under cyclic loading.

The master curve of static strength can be shown by the following equation based on ATM-2.

$$\log \sigma_f(t', T_0, P_f) = \log \sigma_{t_0}(t_0', T_0) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] - n_r \log \left[\frac{D^*(t', T_0)}{D_c(t_0', T_0)} \right] \quad (1)$$

The first term of right part shows the reference strength (scale parameter for the static strength) at reduced reference time t_0' under the reference temperature T_0 . The second term shows the scatter of static strength as the function of failure probability P_f based on condition (A). α is the shape parameter for the strength. The third term shows the variation by the viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin which depend on temperature and load histories. n_r is the material parameter. The viscoelastic compliance D^* in (1) can be shown by the following equation,

$$D^*(t', T_0) = \frac{\varepsilon(t', T_0)}{\sigma(t', T_0)} = \frac{\int_0^{t'} D_c(t' - \tau', T_0) \frac{d\sigma(\tau')}{d\tau'} d\tau'}{\sigma(t', T_0)}$$

$$t' = \int_0^{t'} \frac{d\tau}{a_{T_0}(T(\tau))} \quad (2)$$

where D_c shows the creep compliance of matrix resin and $\sigma(\tau')$ shows the stress history. t' is the reduced time at T_0 , a_{T_0} shows the time-temperature shift factor of matrix resin and $T(\tau)$ shows the temperature history. The viscoelastic compliance D^* under constant deformation rate loading (static loading) can be shown by

$$D^*(t', T_0) \cong D_c(t'/2, T_0)$$

Condition C is not considered here because the static loading employed in the tests is monotonic.

3 Experimental Procedures

Two kinds of unidirectional CFRP laminates were employed in this study. One is T300/EP which consists of carbon fiber T300 and epoxy resin 2500 (Toray). The laminates were cured by autoclave technique at 135°C for 2hours and then post-cured at 160°C for 2hours. The aging treatment for post-cured specimen was conducted at 110°C for 50hours. The Wet specimens by soaking the aged specimen (Dry specimen) in hot water of 95°C for 121hours for 1mm thick specimen in longitudinal direction, 95°C for 144hours for 2mm thick specimen in longitudinal direction and 95°C for 121hours for 2mm thick specimen in transverse direction were respectively prepared. The water content of all of wet specimen was 1.9wt%. The other is the T700/VE which consists of carbon fiber T700 unidirectional non-crimp fabric (Toray) and vinylester resin Neopol 8250L (Japan U-PICA). The laminates were molded by vacuum assisted resin transfer molding technique and then cured at room temperature for 24hours. The post-cure is conducted at 150°C for 2hours. The Wet specimens by soaking the aged specimen (Dry specimen) in hot water of 95°C for 25hours for 1mm thick specimen in longitudinal direction, 95°C for 50hours for 2mm thick specimens in longitudinal and transverse directions were respectively prepared. The water content of wet specimen was 0.5wt%.

The dynamic viscoelastic tests for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP were carried out at various frequencies and temperatures to construct the master curve of creep compliance for matrix resin. The static tests for typical four directions of unidirectional CFRP were carried out at various temperatures to construct the master curves of static

strength for unidirectional CFRP. Longitudinal tension tests were carried out according with SACMA 4R-94. Longitudinal bending tests under static and fatigue loadings were carried out according with ISO 14125 to get the longitudinal compressive static strengths. Transverse bending tests were carried out according with ISO 14125 to get the transverse tensile static strengths. Transverse compression tests under static and fatigue loadings were carried out according with SACMA 1R-94.

4 Results and Discussion

4.1 Viscoelastic behaviour of matrix resin

The left side of Fig.1 shows the loss tangent $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP (Dry specimen) versus time t , where t is the inverse of frequency. The right side shows the master curve of $\tan \delta$ which is constructed by shifting $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since $\tan \delta$ at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for $\tan \delta$ for the transverse direction of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP. The master curve of $\tan \delta$ for Wet specimens can be also constructed as shown in Fig.1. The TTSP is also applicable for $\tan \delta$ under wet condition. The master curve of $\tan \delta$ is shifted to the left side by water absorption as shown in Fig.1.

The left side of Fig.2 shows the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP (Dry specimen) versus time t . The right side shows the master curve of E' which is constructed by shifting E' at various constant temperatures along the logarithmic scale of t using the same shift amount for $\tan \delta$ and logarithmic scale of E' until they overlapped each other, for the reduced time t' at the reference temperature $T_0=25^\circ\text{C}$. Since E' at various constant temperatures can be superimposed so that a smooth curve is constructed, the TTSP is applicable for E' for the transverse direction of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP. The master curve of E' for Wet specimens can be also constructed as shown in Fig.2. The TTSP is also applicable for E' under wet condition.

The time-temperature shift factor $a_{T_0}(T)$ which is the horizontal shift amount shown in the upper portion of Fig.3 can be formulated by the following equation,

$$\log a_{T_0}(T) = \frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) H(T_g - T) + \left[\frac{\Delta H_1}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T_g} - \frac{1}{T_0} \right) + \frac{\Delta H_2}{2.303G} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (4)$$

where G is the gas constant, 8.314×10^{-3} [kJ/(K•mol)], ΔH_1 and ΔH_2 are the activation energies below and above the glass transition temperature T_g , respectively. H is the Heaviside step function.

The temperature shift factor $b_{T_0}(T)$ which is the amount of vertical shift shown in the lower portion of Fig.3 can be fit with the following equation:

$$\log b_{T_0}(T) = \left[\sum_{i=0}^4 b_i (T - T_0)^i \right] H(T_g - T) + \left[\sum_{i=0}^4 b_i (T_g - T_0)^i + \log \frac{T_g}{T} \right] (1 - H(T_g - T)) \quad (5)$$

(a) T300/EP

where b_i are the fitting parameters.

The creep compliance D_c of matrix resin was back-calculated from the storage modulus E' for the transverse direction of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP using [3]

$$D_c(t) \cong 1/E(t), \quad E(t) \cong E'(\omega) |_{\omega \rightarrow 2/\pi} \quad (6)$$

and approximate averaging method by Uemura [4].

The master curves of back-calculated D_c of two kinds of matrix resin are shown in Fig.4. The master curve of D_c can be formulated by the following equation,

$$\log D_c = \log D_{c,0}(t'_0, T_0) + \log \left[\left(\frac{t'}{t'_0} \right)^{m_g} + \left(\frac{t'}{t'_g} \right)^{m_r} \right] \quad (7)$$

where $D_{c,0}$ is the creep compliance at reduced reference time t'_0 and reference temperature T_0 , and t'_g is the glassy reduced time on T_0 , and m_g and m_r are the gradients in glassy and rubbery regions of D_c master curve. Parameters obtained from the formulations for $a_{T_0}(T)$, $b_{T_0}(T)$, and D_c are listed in Table I.

(b) T700/VE

Fig.1 Master curves of loss tangent for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

(a) T300/EP

(b) T700/VE

Fig.2 Master curves of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

(a) T300/EP

(b) T700/VE

Fig.3 Shift factors of storage modulus for transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Fig.4 Master curves of creep compliance for matrix resin calculated from the storage modulus for the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Table I Parameters for master curve and shift factors of creep compliance for matrix resin

	T300/EP		T700/VE	
	Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
T_0 [°C]	25	25	25	25
T_g [°C]	110	65	110	(90)
D_{c0} [1/GPa]	0.337	0.351	0.337	0.339
t'_0 [min]	1	1	1	1
t'_g [min]	1.54E06	2.34E03	1.36E06	(1.80E04)
m_g	0.0101	0.0348	0.00893	0.0195
m_r	0.405	0.466	0.373	(0.373)
ΔH_1 [kJ/mol]	132	150	128	129
ΔH_2 [kJ/mol]	517	547	576	-
b_0	1.65E-02	0.150	3.24E-04	-8.77E-03
b_1	-1.86E-03	-1.39E-02	-1.99E-04	1.45E-04
b_2	6.64E-05	4.26E-04	8.64E-06	9.63E-06
b_3	-8.29E-07	-4.71E-06	-1.75E-08	-
b_4	3.81E-09	1.73E-08	-1.71E-10	-

4.2 Master curves of static strengths for unidirectional CFRP

Figures 5 and 6 show the master curves of static strengths for longitudinal tension X , longitudinal compression X' , transverse tension Y and transverse compression Y' for Dry and Wet specimens of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP obtained from the strength data at various temperatures by using the time-temperature shift factors a_{T_0} shown in Fig.3. The solid and dotted curves in these figures show the fitting curves by Eq.(1) using the master curves of creep compliance of matrix resin in Fig.4. The parameters obtained by formulation are shown in Table II. From these figures, the static strengths of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP decrease with increasing time, temperature and water absorption. The time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of unidirectional CFRP are different with the loading direction.

4.3 Relationship between static strengths and viscoelasticity of matrix resin

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the static strength of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP and the viscoelastic compliance of corresponding matrix resin. The slope of this relation corresponds to the parameter n_r in Table II. The slope depends on the loading direction while that changes scarcely with water absorption. It is cleared from these facts that the time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of unidirectional CFRP can be uniquely determined by the viscoelastic behavior of corresponding matrix resin.

Figures 8 and 9 focuses to the comparison of relationships about each strength of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP and the viscoelasticity of corresponding matrix resin. All cases of the relationship are uniquely determined for the viscoelastic behavior of corresponding matrix, however the relationship is not always fitted by a straight line. That of the compressive strength of transverse direction Y' is accurately fitted by curves.

Fig.5 Master curves of tensile and compressive strengths in the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP

Fig.6 Master curves of tensile and compressive strengths in the transverse direction of unidirectional CFRP

Table II Parameters for master curve of static strength of unidirectional CFRP

		T300/EP		T700/VE	
		Dry	Wet	Dry	Wet
X	σ_{s0} [MPa]	1700	1675	2174	1881
	n_r	0.0762	0.0528	0.0633	0.122
	α	14.7	20.7	22.9	22.7
X'	σ_{s0} [MPa]	1446	1535	1416	1389
	n_r	0.316	0.356	0.738	1.01
	α	10.0	7.18	6.92	21.1
Y	σ_{s0} [MPa]	121	90.6	47.9	34.4
	n_r	0.387	0.371	0.362	0.436
	α	7.04	7.97	14.7	32.4
Y'	σ_{s0} [MPa]	156	131	164	136
	n_r	0.0868	0.130	0.713	1.06
	α	5.68	11.4	5.92	31.2

(a) T300/EP

(b) T700/VE

Fig.7 Static strength of unidirectional CFRP versus viscoelastic compliance of matrix resin

(a) Longitudinal/tensile X

(b) Longitudinal/compressive X'

Fig.8 Comparison of relationship between static strength of unidirectional CFRP and viscoelasticity of matrix resin (X and X')

(a) Transverse/tensile Y

(b) Transverse/compressive Y'

Fig.9 Comparison of relationship between static strength of unidirectional CFRP and viscoelasticity of matrix resin (Y and Y')

5 Conclusion

A general and rigorous advanced accelerated testing methodology (ATM-2) for the long-term life prediction of polymer composites exposed to an actual loading having general stress and temperature history has been proposed. The tensile and compressive static strengths in the longitudinal and transverse directions of two kinds of unidirectional CFRP under wet condition are evaluated using ATM-2. The applicability of ATM-2 can be confirmed for these static strengths. The time, temperature and water absorption dependencies of static strength of unidirectional CFRP can be determined by the viscoelastic behavior of matrix resin.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the Office of Naval Research for supporting this work through an ONR award with Dr. Yapa Rajapakse as the ONR Program Officer. Our

award is numbered to N62909-12-1-7024 and titled "Accelerated Testing Methodology for Long-Term Durability of CFRP Structures for Marine Use". The authors thank Professor Richard Christensen at Stanford University as the consultant of this project and Toray Industries, Inc. as the supplier of CFRP laminates.

References

1. Y. Miyano, M. Nakada and H. Cai, J. Composite Materials, 42, 1897 (2008)
2. R. M. Christensen and Y. Miyano, Int. J. Fracture, 137, 77 (2006)
3. R. M. Christensen, Theory of Viscoelasticity, 2nd edition, Dover Publications, Inc., 1982, pp.142.
4. M. Uemura and N. Yamada, J. Soc. Material Sci., Japan, 24, 156 (1975).